

ATTRACTING CHILDREN WITH HEARING DEFECTS IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article talks about the methods of teaching hearing impaired children in regular classes and their place in society, and the work being done for this purpose. Examples of the effective activity of pedagogues, their deep and diverse professional knowledge, methods of education are presented.

Key words: deaf pedagogy, pedagogical skills, Cochlear implantation, speech deficiency, mental retardation.

Introduction:

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PF-5712 inclusive education in general education schools in Uzbekistan is expected to be introduced.

In the next academic year, 24% of children with special educational needs, and by 2025, 40% are expected to attend regular schools. In recent times, we often come across the concept of inclusive education, many people understand this concept as the fact that children with disabilities study in the same school, in the same class, and sit at the same desk as healthy children. Actually, not only that. Inclusive education means that all children are educated in the same school and in the same classroom - in the same environment. That is, a child with disabilities should be able to study with the same attention as healthy children. A child of a low-income family should not go to an unrenovated school just because he is from a poor family," said Aybek Isakov, chairman of the Disabled People's Association of Uzbekistan.

The main part: Children with hearing impairment (*conductive, sensorineural and mixed*), depending on the time of the disorder (*before the formation of speech or when speech is already formed*) (*hearing loss, expressed to one degree or another and deafness*) differ in degree. In addition, children in this category may have additional diseases. There are three main categories of hearing impaired children: deaf, hard of hearing and late hearing. Deaf children have profound, permanent binaural hearing that can be inherited, congenital, or acquired in early childhood—before speech is acquired. They do not perceive the speech volume of the speech, and without special (*corrective*) education, oral speech does not develop. The use of hearing aids or cochlear implants is a prerequisite for their speech development. However, even when using hearing aids or implants, they have difficulty perceiving and understanding the speech of others. Hearing impaired children have different levels of hearing impairment (mild, moderate, significant and severe), that is, from small difficulties in understanding whispering speech to complete lack of understanding of the volume of speech. They can independently, at least to a minimum, collect vocabulary and master oral speech. However,

these children do best in a specially organized, corrective and developmental process. The need and procedure for using hearing aids is determined by specialists (*deafologist and deaf-deaf pedagogue*). Delayed children are children who have lost their ability to hear due to any disease or trauma, after they have mastered speech, i.e. at the age of two to three years and beyond. Hearing ability is different - common, near-deaf or hearing-impaired. The main task is to preserve their speech and develop it further. In the first year of life, children with low hearing ability have signs of delay in the development of auditory perception: auditory concentration is not noted or poorly expressed; no search for the sound source (*after three months of life*). The child does not respond to the mother's voice; after six months, he does not have screams and voice modulation; he does not imitate the voice of adults; after nine months, the child does not understand the speech addressed to him.

Hearing-impaired children receive speech in three ways - auditory-visual, auditory, visual. The most complete auditory-visual method is when the child sees the speaker's face and lips and "hears" him using a hearing aid Cochlear implant. The ability to hear inevitably leads to different features of the development of the cognitive field: visual perception has a smaller volume, slow pace, differs in uncertainty; characterized by difficulties in attention distribution, switching; figurative memory is better developed than verbal memory; the mental operations of analysis are superior to those of synthesis. Deaf and hard-of-hearing preschool children face difficulties in forming the main types of activities. The most obvious features in game development. Without special training, they will not form a fully developed role-playing game. In the personal sphere, hypertrophic dependence, self-doubt, and fear stand out, especially for close adults. The reaction to new conditions (*unfamiliar tasks, situation, unknown people*) can take different forms: care, refusal to communicate with a stranger, capriciousness and aggression.

Hearing-impaired children are characterized by poverty of emotional manifestations; they do not always understand the feelings of others in certain situations, they do not know how to react to them it is difficult to express feelings and desires when communicating with others. These children differ in the level of speech development. Hearing impairment, first of all, negatively affects the state of the auditory analyzer - the formation of a specific mental function that depends on the formation of speech.

Children of the first group have difficulties in perceiving individual elements of speech and whispering. They have very large vocabularies, only individual sounds are mispronounced, allow agrammatisms, have little difficulty in making a coherent statement. They can be successfully studied and trained in general developing pre-school educational organizations with minimal use of special material and technical resources.

The second group includes children who need corrective and pedagogical work from the age of seven. They are characterized by difficulties in understanding speech, the amount of vocabulary is reduced compared to listeners; they pronounce sounds distorted, do not have intonation design of speech, have constant agrammatisms; identifying ambiguity while creating a coherent statement. Children of the second group need special material-technical and corrective-developmental conditions in a preschool educational institution of the general development type, or they can visit special (*corrective*) combined preschool educational institutions.

The third group is children with serious structural underdevelopment of speech. They pay attention to serious difficulties in speech perception, sharply limited vocabulary,

expressed agrammatisms, lack of coherent statements. They are recommended to teach and train at it is possible to enter a kindergarten of general development type only if there is a full set of material and technical resources and comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support. However, the opportunities for hearing-impaired children are enormous. Effective hearing With cochlear implantation, in the conditions of qualified pedagogical support organized in the optimal time (*infancy and early age*), even deaf preschool children can approach their peers in mental and speech development. When entering school (*general education institution*), hearing impaired students, as a rule, have different levels of mental and speech development. It depends on the degree of hearing loss, the time of its appearance, the adequacy of medical rehabilitation (correction of hearing), the availability of timely, systematic, qualified psychological and pedagogical support and, of course, the specific characteristics of raising a child in the family. In deaf pedagogy, the main features of speech development of deaf and hard-of-hearing students are highlighted:

- at the level of production - pronunciation disorder; insufficient assimilation of the sound content of words, which is manifested in errors in their pronunciation and writing;
- lexical level-limited vocabulary, misunderstanding and incorrect use of words, often associated with the complete acquisition of contextual meaning;
- at the grammatical level - errors in the grammatical structure of speech, especially errors in the acquisition and repetition of speech structures;
- at the syntactic level - difficulties in perceiving words, phrases in an unconventional reverse order, sentences and limitations in understanding the read text.

To organize the educational process, one of the most important features of the knowledge and personal development of students should show the following:

- decreased attention, its stability, low switching speed and difficulties there, the predominance of conceptual forms of thinking, the dependence of verbal and logical thinking on the level of speech development;
- misunderstandings and difficulties in distinguishing the emotional state of others, poverty of one's own emotional manifestations;
- the presence of a number of negative situations - self-doubt, fear, hypertrophic dependence on close adults, sometimes low self-esteem and aggression;
- priority communication with the teacher and restrictions on interaction with classmates.

The ability to hear leads not only to the underdevelopment of speech, but also to the peculiarities of mental development in general. In this regard, the special educational needs of the deaf and hard of hearing are primarily related to difficulties in perceiving speech, understanding and using verbal information, which leads to interaction with others and the formation of a personal sphere. When teaching and educating children with hearing impairment, their special educational needs should be taken into account:

- changing study plans and programs, increasing study time;
- in teaching based on special methods and techniques;
- in the development of language skills by teaching auditory-visual perception of speech and various types of communication;
- distinguish speech and non-speech sounds in the development of hearing and apply these skills in various everyday and communicative situations;

- in complete and accurate perception of information of educational and social importance;
- the need for speech communication and being in a communicative environment as a condition for mastering its various means;
- in the development and improvement of verbal-logical thinking and verbal memory;
- in the development of social competences and the emotional sphere.

Integrated education of a child with hearing impairment, inclusive or planned, based on the conclusion of Pmpk. In order to choose an inclusive model (*that is, studying in a regular class*), it is important to consider: the degree of hearing impairment and the time of its appearance; the state of speech development and communication skills, the ability to use residual hearing in communicative and cognitive situations. Safety of mind, good memory, inventiveness, voluntary qualities, socially acceptable social behavior skills and psychological stability are also required for successful learning in an inclusive classroom. A hearing-impaired child should receive quality hearing immediately in case of hearing loss and spend early and preschool childhood in a special (*remedial*) developmental education system. Learning motivation is important; comfortable living conditions in the family, parents or close adults are ready to work closely with the school and actively participate in the child's education and development. These conditions mean that inclusive education (*the inclusion of one or more hearing-impaired students in a regular public school classroom*) is effective only for children with intelligence and a mild form of developmental disorder, which corresponds to the level of the special education standard.

For children with special educational needs due to the deterioration of hearing and the significant underdevelopment of speech and communicative competences, it is necessary to significantly change the curriculum and extend the study time, in an integrated class, that is, with special educational needs it is recommended to study in a special class. *As part of the public school.* The successful solution of educational problems largely depends on the creation of a system of "temporary solutions" for the student with hearing impairment. For this, the teacher chooses teaching methods, tools and forms that match the tasks and capabilities of the child and uses them in the necessary combinations. General pedagogical methods are used in combination with each other and with the use of special techniques and tools that help to form specific educational technologies. Their implementation is carried out taking into account the main difficulties in teaching children with hearing impairment, for example: limited hearing ability, the specificity of speech development, and the characteristics of the development of cognitive and personal spheres. The choice of methods and techniques for organizing the educational process of a hearing-impaired child in inclusive schools, its composition, is determined by a number of factors, the most important of which are: the level of readiness of the hearing-impaired child to study in a general education school; effectiveness of the teacher's cooperation and interaction with the deaf pedagogue and the child's parents; parents' ability to regularly work with the child at home and in the afternoon; the level of adaptation of a student with deaf hearing loss in the children's group and the possibility of organizing cooperation with classmates; the adequacy of the organization of the workplace of the teacher and the student with impaired hearing; the need to solve some problems during the lesson stimulating listening and visual attention, correcting speech errors and strengthening grammatically correct speech skills; reserving and explaining words

and phrases; providing special assistance. In inclusive education with deaf and hard-of-hearing children, visual methods are most needed, especially in the early stages of education. activates, helps to increase cognitive activity in general, forms motivation for communication with peers, and also creates favorable conditions for organizing cooperation in the student team. Visual methods include manuals (*natural objects and their models, posters, tables, diagrams, pictures, etc.*), including demonstrations of instruments, experiments, films and videos, computer presentations, etc. The use of visual methods requires the teacher to take into account the characteristics of hearing-impaired schoolchildren (*small volume of perception, its slow pace, uncertainty, etc.*) informing about the topic, content and tasks of the research, strict dosage and composition of the recommended material. It is necessary to prepare oral comments in advance, summarize information, emphasize the main thing in the content. The use of visual methods provides support for forced speech.

Practical teaching methods (*exercise method, dramatization, laboratory and practical work, games, etc.*) are widely used in the process of teaching hearing impaired children to expand their ability to know reality, to form objective and universal competencies. Usually, practical, visual and verbal methods are used in complex conditions, which allows children with hearing impairment to form the sensorimotor basis of understanding of the world, more precisely, to fully perceive and understand information, store and process it. Practical the use of methods requires taking into account the characteristics of hearing-impaired schoolchildren (*limited life and practical experience, peculiarities of understanding verbal instructions, predominance of visual forms of thinking, etc.*). The most common practical method is practice - the systematic and repeated execution of an action in order to master it or improve the quality of its execution. Practicing the hearing impaired student learns to focus on the lesson plan; the teacher initially offers algorithmic instructions to the child, focuses on starting his movement and encourages him to clearly perceive the instructions, analyze the actions, summarize the results of the activity and consolidate the acquired experience in words. In addition, the child is offered such activities as reading and completing tasks together with the teacher or classmate; show a sample of the task to explain and practice with the teacher or a friend; to independently read the child's task and explain (*interpret*) his actions in detail during its implementation, first with the teacher, and then with a friend or in a group, when the child begins to understand the instructions and performs the exercises independently, it is necessary to stop the support in time when it is active in the process of mutual education. During the performance of laboratory and practical work, the teacher demonstrates the methods of observation and inspection of objects and various technologies of working with them, including in changing conditions. The use of didactic, role-playing games activates children's cognitive activity, stimulates personal development, helps to ensure natural interaction and communication with a hearing impaired child in a normal children's community. Oral teaching methods (story, conversation, explanation, etc.) have the most distinctive features in the process of teaching hearing impaired children and should be combined with visual and practical methods at the initial stages. The specific characteristics of children's speech development require compliance with certain conditions when using oral methods: following the teacher's or students' oral statements or stories in written, schematic or visual form; drawing children's attention to the topic of the lesson, new words and definitions using game techniques; dramatization; algorithmic and structured explanation of new material at the initial stages, abstracts, lists, schemes on a short personal card or board;

use of special techniques used in deaf pedagogy in working with hearing impaired children. Forms of organization of teaching and upbringing of hearing impaired children are also an important component in conditions of inclusion. In the conditions of the traditional classroom system existing in the school, it is necessary to widely use forms of work such as group, small group (*communities*), pair work and tutor's individual work with students. Deaf or hard-of-hearing children have good opportunities to participate in group activities of the class. The participation of a child who does not work in a research or creative project with other students, presenting and defending these projects has great potential.

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